

STANDING TO SUE REGULATION IN THE NEW DIRECTIVE OF EUROPEAN COLLECTIVE REDRESS AND THE ACCESS TO JUSTICE RIGHT.

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ABSTRACT

After more than a decade of studies, workshops and surveys, European Commission has accompanied a “Proposal of Directive on representative actions for the protection of the collective interest of consumers, and repealing Directive 2009/22/CE” to the “New Deal for Consumers” with the goal of protecting European consumers from the infringements of the Union law in an economic globalization and digitalization era.

At this date this Proposal has been amended by European Parliament in its first reading and it starts the final stage of the Directive with the European Union Council, which has also approved its general approach on the matter. The 2018 Study from Commission highlights that only nineteen Member States have a collective compensatory redress tool in their procedural legislation. Consequently, it was necessary to set out a similar procedure in all the countries in order to standardize the protection of the interest of consumers.

Europe has always feared the abuses seen in the class action system in USA. For this reason, it has tried to find a good balance between access to justice right and the safeguards to avoid the unmeritorious claims. In some cases, the safeguards are suitable mechanisms to reach the fair play and avoid the exclusive interest of lawyer companies. But in others the safeguards restrict the access to justice right. This happens when Directive rules that only qualified entities are able to represent the interest of the group of consumers. The access to justice is a fundamental right that must weigh more in this careful conflict of rights of interest. The consumers have to be able to be represented by other consumer in the same situation, especially when there are other efficient mechanisms to avoid the abuse of attorneys. This is the argument offered in this article, after studying the class action system and its background in Europe.

KEYWORDS

CLASS ACTION, COLLECTIVE REDRESS, CONSUMER, INJUNCTIVE, ACCESS TO JUSTICE, DIRECTIVE REDRESS, CROSS-BORDER.

Summary: 1. Introduction. 2. The Class Actions in the United States. 2.1 Historical Development. 2.2 Current Procedure. 2.3. Efficiency, abuse and correction. 3. The European Collective Redress. 3.1 Background. 3.2 General principles of Proposal of Directive on representative actions. 4. Conclusion.

1. Introduction.

There is a recent proposal of Directive in the European Union about collective actions. It consists of a minimum that all State members have to meet, and pursues, following its background, to foster the access to justice and protect the consumer right.

The new text has been adopted by the Parliament in its first reading/single reading (and it has amended the Commission proposal)¹. This means that it starts the final shape that the legislation will take with the Council, which has also approved its general approach on the matter.²

Therefore, and after several years without a real success of collective actions in most part of the European countries, it is high time of wondering if this regulation provides consumers with a sufficient tool to achieve the full compensation and if it really enforces a high level of protection and access to justice.

Taking into account that a thorough review of all legislation about European class actions is a huge task for a single article, the aim of this essay is to analyse only a part of it. In this vein, the part of regulation of “standing to sue” is the crucial

¹ In order to know the amendments from the Parliament vid:

Representative actions for the protection of collective interests of consumers, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/ATAG/2019/635588/EPRS_AT A\(2019\)635588_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/ATAG/2019/635588/EPRS_AT A(2019)635588_EN.pdf)

²Nonetheless most of calendar of European Institution has been modified at this time due to force majeure as a result of the spread of coronavirus disease (COVID-19). The legislative activities, with exceptions of legislative priorities, have been postponed.

piece of the system to ensure the access to justice for the consumer.

For this goal, it seems necessary to study the well-known system of class action from United States and after, to do a comparison with the European legislation, considering the background of both legislation and their sources.

It will be concluded that including a individual consumer or group of consumers in the list of agents that can sue in court pretending a judgement, not only might increase the effectiveness of the collective action but also achieve the deterrence goal in an environment with a gap in the area of private enforcement. This inclusion would not have involved the abuse of litigation that the European Union tries to avoid by all means.

2. The Class actions in the United States.

2.1 Historical development.

To start with, before doing the description of the current procedure of class actions in the USA, it is important to do a summarized description of its origin. The class actions were imported from England in 1800 as a tool to avoid the rigid rules of necessary parties to cover situations³ and despite the fact they were not thought primarily for organizational suits, the first suits were from organizations and not from individual persons, such as suits by trade unions, in which members voluntarily associated, in case of having a problem, delegating litigation rights to organizational representatives.

In 1938, after its predecessor Rule, Equity 48, it was promulgated the Rule 23 just to try to encourage the individual use of class actions. This rule distinguished among three types of class actions: “true” (joint or common right), “hybrid” (several rights to a specific property) and “spurious” (several rights having commonality).⁴

The first two types were precursors of the so-called mandatory classes but the third one was a creation designed to facilitate permissive joinder among unorganized members who shared a common interest and rather than depending

³ “where the parties are very numerous, and the court perceives, that it will be almost impossible to bring them all before the court; or where the question is of general interest, and a few may sue for the benefit of the whole; or where the parties form a part of a voluntary association for public or private purposes, and may be fairly supposed to represent the rights and interest of the whole...West. Randall 29.F cas. 718, 722 (C.C.D.R.I 1820) (N.º 17,424) (Story, J). A more detailed class-action typology can be found at Joseph Shory (...). Reference 11. In: Scott Dodson, An opt-in Option for Class Actions, 115 Mich. I. Rev 171 (2016). Available at <https://repository.law.umich.edu/mir/vol115/iss2/1>.

⁴ Scott Dodson, An opt-in Option for Class Actions, 115 Mich. I. Rev 171 (2016). Available at <https://repository.law.umich.edu/mir/vol115/iss2/1>.

upon members ex ante consent, required post hoc consent in the form of an opt-in mechanism⁵.

It is strongly believed that the application of the Rule was chaotic between the judges which didn't apply strictly the rules of each action and they arbitrarily did the choice of each figure.

After this period, the decade of 1960's started with a remarkable social/political change. It was the time of strengthening civil rights, and politicians, judges and academics saw in the class action system the mechanism for reinforcing the protection of civil rights. In 1966, Rule 23 is revised seeking, among other goals, to enable low-value claims (mass tort). It was thought that if this kind of claims was encouraged, the behavior of corporations would be more careful (deterrence).

Accordingly, the new Rule 23 would require the famous elements that will be dealt with next in this text: numerosity, commonality, typicality, etc. Furthermore, it is done a new classification between "mandatory class", "group remedy classes" and "economy-based", common-interest classes. This last action Rule 23 (b) (3) was seen like a vehicle for reassuring the potential damage interest of groups of members of the unaffiliated claimants.

In 1970's the corporate community, concerned by the consequences of the increased use of class actions, begun to criticize the system of the Rule 23, which was called "Frankenstein monster" due to the abuse of the well-known tactics of blackmail settlements by the lawyers.

Finally, and after a brief initial period of expansive application of Rule 23, the courts began an era of retrenchment that continues to this day ("scrupulous scrutiny").

2.2 Procedure of class action in 23 Rule.

⁵Opt-out classes, which include all members who do not opt out, tend to be more inclusive than opt-in classes, which include only members who affirmatively opt in. Because of inertia, an opt-in regime would result in "drastically reduce(d) numbers of class members." (...) Proponents of opt-in classes, by contrast, focus on protecting absent class members and defendants. Opt-in classes ensure true consent. Class members give up their rights to individual litigation when they join a preclusive class, and accordingly, some indication of consent is important. However in an opt-out class, any person within the scope of the class definition is a class member by default unless she affirmatively excludes herself from the class and preserves her right to litigate individually. Those who favor class actions see the opt-out model as a crucial feature of maintaining a strong and effective class mechanism, while those who disfavor class actions see the opt-in model as an important vehicle for restricting them. Scott Dodson, An opt-in Option for Class Actions, 115 Mich. I. Rev 171 (2016). Available at <https://repository.law.umich.edu/mir/vol115/iss2/1>.

Firstly it has to be said that if the European Collective redress is compared with the USA class action it is because in this last state the collective actions have reached a considerable success but it is also strongly believed that the phenomenon has ended with a huge abuse of this device by the lawyer associations which has occasionally harmed the economy of the big enterprises.

Then, the USA class actions have overwent several changes over the last few years to avoid the numerous claims against enterprises where the biggest amount of money was for the lawyer. The reason for this abuses will be explained below:

To start with it would be interesting to explain that European and North-American systems are completely different, so before starting to describe the procedure, it is necessary to take into account two or three features that characterize the USA system.

On one hand, the United States are a common law country, and as a consequence the judge has a discretionary power, more power than a judge from a civil law system where all the procedure is in the law. On the other hand, once private litigation has started, judges are usually passive regarding introducing facts, frame dispute and presenting evidence. Lawyers play a role so dominant in litigation that this system has been called "adversarial legalism"⁽⁶⁾. Besides, after settlement or judgement, each plaintiff will pay only his own lawyer and fees (contingency fees).

It is also important to remember another feature in USA system, which is the multiple forum. In the USA there are a Federal jurisdiction and the rest of States jurisdictions. All of them can be possible jurisdictions for one class action. The procedure in the Federal regulation is in the Rule 23 of Federal Rules of Civil Procedure and most of states have copied this regulation⁷.

Having said that, in the USA a class action is initiated by filing a complaint by a named plaintiff (potential consumer or actual damaged) on behalf of a class formed of members similarly situated. If defendants choose to file a motion to dismiss and the case survives, then in certain cases may be appropriate for the Court to appoint a "lead plaintiff" and "lead counsel", to represent the putative class even before class certification. In appointing lead plaintiff, the court is instructed to "adopt a presumption" in favour of plaintiffs with "the largest

⁶Adversarial legalism. "Cross-Border Collective Redress in the European Union and Private International Law Rules on Jurisdiction." Madrid, 2017. Alexia Pato.

⁷ Forum shopping and the Class Action Fairness Act in order to avoid strategies regarding forum selection to a certain extent. "Cross-Border Collective Redress in the European Union and Private International Law Rules on Jurisdiction." Madrid, 2017. Alexia Pato.

financial interest” in the class action.

The next step consists of determining if this complaint should be “certified”, this is if the judge confirms that case is appropriate for class action treatment. If plaintiff succeeds, the rest of the class members are automatically bound by the court final judgment.

The certification in the class actions is the most important step in all the procedure due to the fact that the plaintiff who achieves this certification will have got a very strong position in front of a pressured defendant who surely will want to reach a settlement in order to avoid paying a huge amount of money and his discredit (blackmail settlement).

In this vein the American judge (with all his discretionary power) considered if the case in front of him met all the requirements of Rule 23 (a) and one of the requirements of Rule 23 (b). The Rule 23 said:

(a) Prerequisites. One or more members of a class may sue or be sued as representative parties on behalf of all members only if:

(1) the class is so numerous that joinder of all members is impracticable (Numerosity)

(2) there are questions of law or fact common to the class (Commonality).

(3) the claims or defenses of the representative parties are typical of the claims or defenses of the class (Typicality), and,

(4) the representative parties will fairly and adequately protect the interests of the class.

(Standing to sue and adequacy of representation),

This is:

1. The “**Numerosity**” means that it should be not possible to gather all the members of the class through the joinder mechanism. It helps to meet this requirement the concurrence of circumstances such as dispersion of the members of the class or the modest amount of each claim.

2. “**Commonality**”, this means that the facts and the question of law should be common to the class and this justifies the efficiency to centralized in one procedural a thousand of individual claims.

3. “**Typicality**”. The representative plaintiff must have claims and defenses that correspond to the ones of the class.

4. “**Standing to Sue and Adequacy of Representation**”. In USA it is a

general requirement to have “standing to sue” for every kind of lawsuit, but in case of class actions it is necessary to have “standing to sue” an also to be a member of class that represents adequately the absent class members.

Precisely, it is the last requirement the one that helps to understand one of the keys of the large implementation in the procedural practice.

To have Standing to Sue the named plaintiff must have suffered an injury or violation in his protected interest because of an unlawful conduct of the defendant and all the class that he pretends to represent has to be in a similar situation.

Up to here, the system could be similar to the system of continental law but what makes the great difference is that “adequacy of representation” is a requirement that has to meet, on the one hand, the individual plaintiff. He must adequately represent the interest of absent members because all the absent members will be bound by the final judgment of the class action and, on the other hand, what is strange for a system in common law, class counsel has to be also “adequate” to defend absent members interest. (Rule 23, (g)).

This requirement will be checked by the judge who will take into account the potential conflicts of interest between the representative and the class.⁸

Besides the requirements of Rule 23 (a), the attorney seeking class certification must show that the action is maintainable under Rule 23 (b). This part does a classification about several Types of Class Actions, and it is interesting for the sake of this article the subsection 23(b)(3) related to the Class Actions for damage (mass torts, securities, fraud of misrepresentation, financial harm in employment matters, antitrust and consumer fields are usually brought under the (b)(3) category). This rule adds two requirements. Vid:

(b) Types of Class Actions. A class action may be maintained if Rule 23(a) is satisfied and if:

(3) the court finds that the questions of law or fact common to class members predominate over any questions affecting only individual members, and that a class

⁸ Nowadays, the judge checks if the attorney has enough experience, any dangerous interest, responsibility and last but not least, enough resources to finance the class action. *Class action procedure in USA*, <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=a2cd8947-2c7f-42a4-b4eb-09c5fc203c9c>

action is superior to other available methods for fairly and efficiently adjudicating the controversy. The matters pertinent to these findings include:

(A) the class members' interests in individually controlling the prosecution or defense of separate actions;

(B) the extent and nature of any litigation concerning the controversy already begun by or against class members;

(C) the desirability or undesirability of concentrating the litigation of the claims in the particular forum; and

(D) the likely difficulties in managing a class action. (...).

Consequently, the added requirements are:

1. Predominance, it is divided in two demanding circumstances, firstly the link of causality has to be similar (factual predominance) and secondly, the law of the case should be the same law otherwise, if there are different laws from different states, there will be not predominance.

2. Superiority, or if the class action device is the most efficient procedure regarding requisites such as (A) the class members interest.....(B) the likely difficulties in managing a class action....

Following the proceeding, if a claim overcomes this last step because it meets all the requirements of Rules 23(a) and (b), the court will give a "**certification order**". This certification will define the individuals that will be bound by the action and allows appointing the class representative and class counsel, depending on the kind of the class and if it is at this moment or not.

Once the class is certified, and if there is not a settlement, there will be a new step: the notification to the absent class.

The notification is crucial because of notice expands the effects of the judgment of all absent members, even though these did not participate in the trial (request to opting out). It is always required when a class is certified under Rule 23 but also when a settlement has been reached. This way, final resolution of a class action will bind absent class members, and preclude future litigation of their claims against that defendant. Those that opt out, will not be bound by final resolution and may bring a separate case against the defendant based on the same underlying claim (free riders).

After the entry of the certification order, class counsel controls the action and other class members can not participate in most phases of litigation. Rule 23 provides the court flexibility in conducting the proceeding and the rules are similar to other civil proceedings in federal courts.

Finally, it is important to recall that a wide range of proceedings end in a settlement. Thus, if parties want to settle, the courts may resort to use of a “settlement class” mechanism, before entering a certification order. The settlement will grant the class plaintiffs, motion for attorneys fees, and it will determine how funds should be distributed with a “plan of allocation”.

2.3 Reasons for Efficiency and Abuse. Latest corrections.

Why this American system has triggered abusive practices? To answer this question it is required to explain the extent of the efficacy of the system of class actions in fields like consumers law and decide which are the suitable boundaries depending on the economy policies at the time considered.

To understand what has happened in the field of class actions in USA over the last decades it is important to take into account, surprisingly, the factors that have provided efficacy to the system. This is, if somebody has to pay all his attorney’s fees and the damage suffered is small, how can be one single consumer encouraged to sue?

In USA, just to encourage the effectiveness of this actions, the Rule 23 allows the class counsel to lead the case in exchange of a part of the final benefits. As a result a lot of attorneys are appealed by this kind of incentives (paying the cost of fees of notification and the others of the procedure could be a great investment for the future) and over the last few decades it has happened that in so many occasions, the attorneys have been the stakeholders most interested in a fair compensation and it have been them who have gone on the hunt for damaged victims.

The problem of letting the attorney to play the principal role is that, in a myriad of occasions, attorneys had abused of this kind of procedure just only to seek their own benefit. And one portion of the compensation of all the members of a class is a huge amount of money. Even more, if it takes into account that in personal injury cases punitive damages are allowed. Then, there might be an additional monetary relief beyond the value of the harm incurred.⁹

⁹ Actually, there are not so many cases in which it is possible to obtain punitive damage. “Cross-Border Collective Redress in the European Union and Private International Law Rules on Jurisdiction.” Madrid, 2017. Alexia Pato.

The phenomenon described above has increased criticism from the cooperative class and other expertise in the area.

In this context, Rule 23 has been amended several times and judges have also hardened the requirements to obtain the certificate order.

In this vein, judges do a “scrupulous scrutiny” when analysing requirements to obtain certificate order. Indeed, new amendments on class action impose on courts a duty to assess the reasonableness of the fees awarded to class counsel in order to protect the class according to Rule 23 (h). In the same way, it is usual to use methods like calculating the percentage of the fond method, or the price of the hours spent on the case multiplied by an hourly rate adjusted with a percentage based on the complexity of the case, and the risks.

It was also limited the forum shopping, nonetheless the opt-out system never has been questioned.

3. European Union Collective Redress Rules.

3.1 Background.

The European Union’s definition of collective redress has evolved over time.

In 2011, in a Public Consultation Paper, it is acknowledged that this actions could take a variety of forms such as a group of litigation; model case-litigation; actions brought by ombudsmen or consumer organizations; op-out mechanism¹⁰...Nonetheless, the EU has been outlining the notion of collective redress with a special willingness of distinguishing this procedural tool from class actions. This processus will be seen below.

Nowadays, the current proposal distinguishes on two procedural actions: the injunctive and the compensation action, and establishes with certain safeguards¹¹ a minimum of procedural rules that each member state is obliged to adopt in his

¹⁰ As much as tools from the Members States, that have often implemented, from the 1970s until the 1990s, collective redress mechanisms under imprecise labels: acciones colectivas, in Spain, action de groups, in France, etc. but mainly consisted in actions for unjunctive relief and standing to sue was mainly attributed to either, consumer associations or public bodies.

¹¹The rapporteur Geoffroy Didier (EPP, FR) said “This reform strikes the right balance between increasing consumer protection on one hand and the necessary legal safety for companies; it goes even further, by showing that safety and security need to go hand in hand”.

own legislation. This directive pretends to replace the Directive 2009/22/EC and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on injunctions for the protection of consumers interest.

The process starts with the Directive 98/27/CE¹² about injunction actions. This rule allows putting the end of situations generated for unlawful behavior of the enterprise. Following the Article 3 only the consumers associations are allowed to sue. The Injunctions Directive has been codified by Directive 2009/22/EC which is currently in force.

In the first decade of 2000's, cross-border trade and digitalization start to increase and it is seen that it would be useful a system to satisfy with efficacy the rights of consumers harmed in more than one state member.

In this context, it is assigned "The EU Consumer Policy Strategy 2007-2013-Empowering consumers, Enhancing their welfare, Effectively Protecting them". (2017). In this study European Commission establishes that a variety of measures have been taken in order to foster the confidence of consumers. It is considered that the rise of e-commerce generates a new reality where the fragmentation of the internal market has a negative impact. If Europe is based on a market without borders, the consumer rights should be updated to the new challenges. As a consequence, it is suggested not only more cooperation between judicial authorities but also the creation of a collective redress in consumer and antitrust matters to obtain an amount of money in compensation of damage harms.

A year later, in 2008, it is published the "Study Regarding the Problems faced by consumers in obtaining Redress for Infringements of consumer Protection Legislation, and the Economic Consequences of such Problems". Between all the aspects that can deter a consumer to obtain satisfactory redress, litigation cost is perceived as the most important, especially with the small damages. This same year, it was celebrated a workshop ("The consultation on the draft consumer collective Redress Benchmarks and Workshops") where it is noted that business representatives regard collective redress skeptically. They consider an out-of court procedure more interesting. Moreover they are concerned about funding techniques that have to be limited, punitive damages that have to be prohibited and, from their point of view "loser pays" rule has to be respected. In conclusion, they claim that safeguards must be put in place in order to prevent unmeritorious claims and skimming-off procedures must only be ordered by public authorities.

¹² This Directive was repealed by Directive 2009/22/CE.

Legal practitioners and academics usually agree with business representatives, although sometimes adopt a more nuanced approach¹³.

In 2009 it is done “the Green Paper on consumer redress”. At this date, the EU already had set up mechanisms to improve the enforcement of European law: the ADR Directive; the Injunctions Directive and the CPC Regulation to consolidate public enforcement. Nonetheless, it seems not to be enough, given that surveys show an increasing lack of confidence affecting consumers within the European market. The Commission suggests that additional actions should be undertaken. Ad exemplum, establishing a procedure without distinguishing between national and cross-border situations. For this goal four different options are examined, and the idea of ensuring the existence of a judicial collective redress procedure in all Europe, is growingly accepted.

The actions to assess the implementation of collective redress, especially but not only¹⁴ from Commission, were consecutive the following years.

In this regard, the most important document was the “Recommendation of the Commission and Communication” in 2013. Inside, Commission put forward its proposal on collective redress. It has to be highlighted that Collective redress is a crucial mechanism to protect the consumer rights and similarly, foster the internal market. It is said that the principal goal is the access to justice, however the common principles on collective redress following this recommendation could be strongly questioned from the point of view of protecting rights of the consumers, because a group of consumers or a single consumer has not standing to sue. Only representative entities can be subject of these actions. Otherwise, rules mentioned above to limit unmeritorious claims such as prohibition of external funding, punitive damages and contingency fees are considered to have an undoubtfully place in the system.

Finally, the document reflects that an assessment of the implementation of the Recommendation will be carried out by the 26th July 2017 at latest.

In 2007 it is published the REFIT Fitness Check of EU consumer and marketing law, which covered also the Injunctions Directive and in January 2018 the Commission Report on the implementation of Commission Recommendation 2013. Both documents insisted on the necessity of having an uniform process in

¹³ Alexia Pato in Cross-border Collective Redress in the European Union and Private International Law Rules on Jurisdiction.

¹⁴In its 2012 Resolution Towards a Coherent European Approach to Collective Redress, the European Parliament highlighted the need for a horizontal EU approach to collective redress, based on principles respectful of national legal traditions and providing safeguards to avoid abusive litigation. All documents available in the web of the parliament U.E. Vid: References.

all of the member states, with a large scope, compensatory effects and more economic and effective procedure.

Finally, in April 2018 it is released a New Deal for Consumers by the Commission with the aim to ensure stronger consumer protection in the EU. It includes more robust rights for the e-commerce consumer, penalties for violating EU Consumer Law and goes together with the proposal for the new directive that joins the injunction action and the compensatory action. It is said that after adopting this legislation “if a new ‘Dieselgate’ happens in Europe in the future, the member states will be more ready to act”.

3.2 The new regulation: Directive on European Collective Redress.

In 2018 it was revealed that the car manufacturer “Volkswagen” had been selling in all Europe as ‘eco-friendly’ products cars that turned out to have higher emissions than stated. After this reveal, thousands of consumers, being victims of unfair commercial practices such as misleading advertising, showed up. The European Commission, concerned about the outcomes of latest studies regarding the lack of representation action in several member states, decided to accompany a new Directive with “the New Deal for consumers”, that today is part of a negotiation between the Parliament and the Council in accordance with the ordinary legislative procedure.

The Commission proposal has been amended¹⁵ by the Parliament in first reading. This institution has highlighted the goal of enforcing a higher level of protection and access to justice while at the same time ensuring appropriate safeguards to avoid abusive litigation (art. 1). As regard and ad exemplum new requirements about the transparence of funds of representative entities were added.

In this vein, a summarized description of the content of the actual Directive proposal will be done, trying to put the spotlight in the standing to sue rules.

1. Scope: The scope of the Directive will be expanded to cover horizontally different economic sectors such as financial services, energy, telecommunications, health and the environment (art.2).

¹⁵ To see the amendment: “Text adopted by parliament, 1s reading/single reading”. Website European Parliament.

2. Representative actions by qualified entities. (art.4). The Member States have to ensure that only qualified entities can be subjects of representative actions. These entities, that will be placed in a publicly available list, have to meet these requirements:

- 1) *it is properly constituted according to the law of a Member State;*
- 2) *it has legitimate interest in ensuring that provisions of Union law covered by this Directive are complied with;*
- 3) *it has a non-profit making character.*

Member States shall ensure that in particular, consumer organizations and independent public bodies are eligible for the status of qualified entity and they may designate a qualified entity on an ad hoc basis for a particular representative action.

The article 7 sets out that a qualified entity seeking a redress (art.6) has to declare the source of the funds for its activity in general and the funds that it uses to support the action. It needs to demonstrate that it has sufficient financial resources to represent the interest of the consumers.

Moreover, in cases where a third-party funds the action, the judge has to assure at an early stage of the action that the third-party does not influence the decisions of the entity and that the third-party is not a competitor of the defendant. The judge will have to reject the standing of the qualified entity in a specific case.

3. Efficiency of the procedure.

-Art. 8. The member states must promote collective out-of-court settlements, subject to court or administrative authority scrutiny.

-Art. 9. Member states have to ensure “due expediency” of procedures and avoid procedural costs becoming a financial obstacle to bringing representative actions. Consumers will be adequately informed of the outcome of representative actions and how they will benefit from them.

-Art. 10. Final decisions of a court or authority establishing that a trader has infringed the law will be irrefutable evidence in redress actions (within the same Member State) or a rebuttable presumption that the infringement has occurred (for cases brought in another Member State).

-Art. 16. Cross-border representative actions. This rule ensures the mutual recognition of the legal standing of qualified entities. Moreover, it enables qualified entities from different Member States to act jointly within a single representative action in front of a single competent forum.

4. Conclusion.

In 25th January 2018, European Court of Justice, Case c-498/16, rules:

“the Article 16 (1) of Regulation N.º 44/2001 must be interpreted as meaning that it does not apply to the proceedings brought by a consumer for the purpose of asserting, in the courts of the place where he is domiciled, not only his own claims, but also claims assigned by the other consumers domiciled in the same Member States or in non-member countries, in other Member States or in non-member countries”.

This judgement is really related to the rules of private international law but it is interesting from the point of view of studying the standing to sue in the collective redress.

The facts are the following:

“Mr. Schrems has been a user of the social network Facebook since 2008. Initially, he used that social network only for personal purposes under a false name. Since 2010, he has been using a Facebook account solely for his private activities such as exchanging photos, chatting, and posting with approximately 250 Friends. In that account he writes his name using the Cyrillic alphabet in order to prevent any searches under his name. In addition, since 2011, he has opened a Facebook page registered and established by him, in order to report to internet users on his legal proceedings against Facebook Ireland, his lectures, his participation in panel debates and his media appearances, as well as to call for the donation of funds and to publicize his books.

From August 2011, Mr Schrems lodged before the Irish Data Protection Commissioner 23 complaints against Facebook Ireland, one of which gave rise to a reference for a preliminary ruling before the Court (...).

Mr. Schrems has published two books on his legal proceedings against alleged infringements of data protection, has given lectures, some of which were remunerated, in particular with professionals, has registered a number of internet websites such as blogs, online petitions as well as crowdfunding sites to finance legal proceedings against the

defendant in the main proceedings. Furthermore, he has founded an association which seeks to uphold the fundamental right to data protection, has received various prizes and has had assigned to him, by more than 25.000 people worldwide, claims to be brought in the present case.

The association founded by Mr. Schrems and seeking to enforce data protection is a non-profit organization, the purpose of which is to seek to uphold the fundamental right to data protection, to provide the required associated work on communication and the media and on policy clarification. Its objective is to provide financial support for test cases of public interest brought against undertakings which potentially endanger that fundamental right. The necessary costs are also funded and the corresponding donations gathered, administered and distributed”.

In this context, the European Court of Justice recognizes that Mr. Schrems is a consumer so, as the party deemed to be economically weaker, he is able to claim in a Court of his own domicile (art.15 of council Regulation (EC) n°44/2201 of 22 December 2000 on jurisdiction and the recognition and enforcement of judgments in civil and commercial matters). Secondly, European Court sets out that *“an applicant who is not himself a party to the consumer contract in question cannot enjoy the benefit of the jurisdiction relating to consumer contracts. (...). The same considerations must also apply to a consumer to whom the claims of other consumers have been assigned. (...) the fact that a consumer to whom claims have been assigned is, in any event, able to bring proceedings before the courts of the place of his domicile on the basis of claims pursuant to rights vested in him personally under a contract concluded with the defendant, similar to those which have been assigned to him, is not such as to bring those assigned claims also within the jurisdiction of that court (...). “*

After “Directive about collective redress”, this case would be a typical collective claim. And a problem which consumers will have to face is that they will always need to address to a consumer association or similar. Then, if it would be possible to join foreign consumers with national consumers, the consumer organization would sue in its domicile, and after judgment the article 10 of the directive would have effect (where judgment plays a role of presumption) for the absent members. And for the members of the procedure, the rules of recognition on private international law would be needed¹⁶.

¹⁶Art. 2 of the Proposal of Directive, “...is without prejudice to the Union rules on private international law...”

In that regard it is necessary to say that in one case like this, with consumers from different member states, the procedure carries on without clear answers.¹⁷ Even with the rule 16 described above.

On the contrary, one case like this, with consumers from the same state against a foreign enterprise, would be feasible as far as one entitled association was the plaintiff. However, why not allowing an *ad-hoc* group of consumers to claim against an unlawful behavior that harmed them? Is it not true that the bigger the restriction of the subject of the action the bigger the restriction to the access to justice?

In the above case, Mr. Schrems became an expert in the data protection field. Surely he helped to increase awareness about the importance of data protection, and he could explain this hard subject to many laypersons. He could explain to the rest of consumers how they are being damaged and why. Thinking about these facts we can infer that opening this kind of actions to individual consumers is a perfect way to overcome the unsuitable apathy of consumers in the small claims and for this reason it is completely useful to create an space for private enforcement in European market.

It turns out to be clear that economy must be protected. For this, companies have been protected from the unmeritorious claims like it has happened in the United States. Really, all defendants have been protected from unmeritorious claims but not for this reason the access to justice has to be limited. What happened with the Dieselgate? Volkswagen is a vital corporation for the European economy but it acted against law. If all consumers could sue in an easier way, this company would be persuaded from acting again in this way. So, protecting the access to justice right is beneficial for private enforcement.

In these cases and those more complicated like financial clauses or some communications contracts, the consumers must have the power of choosing to make a group and claim for their rights.

This freedom of choice is as well beneficial for meeting other procedural principles. On the one hand, because the big companies often have high qualified lawyers (levelling the playing field) and on the other hand because if qualified entities received money from governments it would be easy to find that in many occasions a conflict of interest would appear. Ad exemplum, consumers of

¹⁷InfoLibre "Trampas" mejoras de la directiva europea sobre las demandas colectivas. Sabela Rodríguez Álvarez. Publicada el 10/01/2020 a las 6:00 (the entities would be able to join consumers from different countries...)

electric or even railway companies. This is the reason why the consumers should have one alternative method to claim for their rights.

In conclusion, if European Union wants to set out a free space of justice and a free market not only it has to advance in the cross-border situation but also has to give the consumers the choice between being represented from an association or from another consumer¹⁸. Furthermore, opening a myriad of actions for protecting rights is always beneficial for the development of a more fair and advanced society.

The unmeritorious claims based on the abuse of claims by attorneys might be avoided with the rules about limitation of fees by the law, assessment of fees by judge and not allowing punitive damages, contingency fees or the benefits or reward of the third-parties who finance the collective action and other methods that limit the benefit of lawyer companies; but not limiting the access to justice right. Otherwise, following the primary principle of justice, all damage produced by unlawful action must be repaired¹⁹.

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¹⁸ The opt-out system or opt-in system would depend of the kind of procedure.

¹⁹ Consumer could be compensated with a ticket of discount or others. It seems odd and unclear the rule of art. 6.3 b) sets out the special case so-called “low-value cases” where consumers have suffered such a small amount of loss that it would be disproportionate to distribute the redress back to the consumers. Member States should not require the mandate of consumers concerned within the representative action and the funds awarded as redress should be directed to a public purpose serving the collective interests of consumers, such as awareness campaigns. “Cross-Border Collective Redress in the European Union and Private International Law Rules on Jurisdiction. “ Madrid, 2017. Alexia Pato.

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